

1 Proofs

1.1 Proof of the Prop. 1 in Sec. III-B

In Sec. III-B of our paper, we mentioned the following proposition, and now we provide its proof here.

Proposition 1. *State transitions in a single sub-strategy (i.e., to reach a particular justice goal) significantly exceed those between different sub-strategies.*

Proof. The system transits from the current sub-strategy (assuming the j th, $j \in [1..n]$) to another one (the next $j \oplus 1$ sub-strategy) if and only if the current state satisfies the conjunction of the j th justice guarantee and the winning-set, i.e., $J_j^z \wedge z$. However, from the transition strategies ρ_2 and ρ_3 (if any) in FDS, we know that to reach such states the system should move at least r steps (recall that r is the iteration times for calculating μY , and $r > 1$). This case occurs for all justice goals, i.e., before conducting one transition from a sub-strategy to another sub-strategy, the system should move r ($r > 1$) steps to reach the switch condition. Hence, transitions in a single sub-strategy exceed those between different sub-strategies and the Prop. 1 stands. Besides, if ρ_2 and ρ_3 are empty (i.e., $r = 1$), meaning that there are only ρ_1 transitions in FDS. This situation occurs when the system-winning set is the whole state space. However, it is meaningless in reality as users do not give a powerful specification. Hence, we don't consider this situation. \square

2 Extra Explanations

2.1 The Step 4 in the NaiveBT Method

The ITE statement in this paper is defined as $ite(D, C_{then})$, which has no C_{else} compared to its original definition, where D is the condition, and C_{then} will be executed when the condition is *true* (or conduct nothing if *false*) [1]. As shown in Table. 1, we summarize three regular patterns (RPs) that emerged in the context of ITE and design corresponding transformation rules for each pattern, where P and P' denote the predicate over \mathcal{V} that describes the current and next states, respectively. BTs are denoted as texts, $Seq/Sel\{\dots\}$ denotes the *Sequence/Selector* node, C^P denotes the *Condition* node with checking condition P , and $A^{P'}$ denotes the *Action* node with action moving to state P' .

For the single ITE pattern RP1, e.g., $ite(\text{"robot at(0,0)"}, \text{"robot' at(0,1)"})$, we construct an equivalent BT by using *Sequence* as root with the *Condition* ("robot at(0,0)?") and the *Action* ("move.to(0,1)") as its children. Note that the inverse pattern $ite(P', P)$ in RP1 has an identical BT form to the general. Since P' describes the next state related to the future, it's not suitable for construction as a condition node that judges whether a condition stands through the current state. Hence, the BT $Seq\{C^{P'}, A^P\}$ is absolutely incorrect. Subsequently, we observe that for the general ITE pattern $ite(P, P')$, if P holds, then P' will hold and be executed; otherwise, P' will not be executed. Similarly,

for the inverse pattern $ite(P', P)$, if P' holds, then P also holds. Both of them have the same truth table. Therefore, for the ITE structure ($ite(D, C_{then})$) in this paper that only contains D and C_{then} , swapping P, P' and constructing the same BT is feasible.

RP2 is the Default Rule, which means that if a variable $R \in \mathcal{X} \cup \mathcal{X}'$ doesn't occur in an ITE sequence (e.g., $ite(r_0=0, ite(r_1=0, r'_0=1))$, while the variable $r'_1 \in \{r_0, r_1, r'_0, r'_1\}$ doesn't in this sequence), it could chose a random value in its legal set $\{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ (if any). RP3 is the Conjunction Rule, meaning that we use *Selector* nodes to conjunct BTs from two individual ITEs.

These RPs are sufficient for recursively constructing BTs from ITEs (Step 4). However, later experiments have evidenced that the NaiveBT method performs poorly no matter on synthesis efficiency or the quality of generated BTs.

Table 1: Regular Patterns of the NaiveBT method

Name	Regular Pattern (RP)	Corresponding BT
RP1	$ite(P, P')$ or $ite(P', P)$;	$Seq\{C^P, A^{P'}\}$
RP2	$ite(P^*, ite(P^*, \dots))$ and the system variable r not occur in it.	$Seq^s\{A^{r=v_1}, \dots, A^{r=v_n}\}$
RP3	$ite(P, P'_1); ite(P, P'_2)$, or $ite(P', P_1); ite(P', P_2)$;	$Sel\{BT_{sub}^1, BT_{sub}^2\}$

2.2 The Prop. 2 in Sec. V-B2

We summarize the conditions for using parallel nodes in Sec. V-B2 in our paper, referred to as Prop 2, and we provide some more detailed descriptions here.

Proposition 2. *A BT could adopt Parallel ($m=1$) as a new root if satisfies the following conditions: 1. it's root is an Selector; 2. no blackboard written conflict or simultaneous condition and action among its children.*

The first condition in Prop. 2 indicates that we consider *Parallel*, specifically, the *Parallel* node with $m=1$, as an alternative to *Selector* nodes as we have explained in the paper that they have similar semantics. When being ticked, the *Selector* routs the *tick* signal to its children in the Depth-First order until any child returns *Success* and the *Selector* succeeds, or all of the children failed which leading to the *Selector* fails, or otherwise return *Running*. Then, for a parallel node with $m=1$, when ticked, it ticks all its children simultaneously and returns *Success* immediately upon the success of any child node. If none of the child nodes succeed, it returns *Failure*; otherwise, it returns *Running*. Therefore, aside from the difference in the order of ticking child nodes, the semantics of Parallel ($m=1$) are very similar to those of Selector nodes.

Then, note that the child nodes of a parallel node execute concurrently. Therefore, we propose the second condition to avoid conflict cases arising from multiple nodes executing simultaneously. In our method, there are two potential

conflict scenarios: blackboard write conflicts caused by action nodes writing to the blackboard simultaneously, and action conflicts due to multiple action nodes executing concurrently.

3 An Example of BT Construction in the EffBT Method

In this part, we present a simple example to explain how the construction algorithm works in EffBT. Assuming that a GR(1) specification ψ with two justice guarantees and a single environment assumptions, and during the realizability check phase, calculating μY got through three iterations. Thus, for the two intermediate strategies stored in $mX[j][r][i]$ and $mY[j][r]$, there are $j \in \{1, \dots, 2\}$, $r \in \{1, \dots, 3\}$, and $i \in \{1\}$. The system-winning set calculated by realizability check is denoted as z .

Overall, for each justice goal j , we construct a subtree to force the system to satisfy it, thus, the overview of the final BT is shown as follows (See Sec. IV-B1 in our paper).

Figure 1: Overview of the Structure of the Example BT from EffBT

Then, take the first subtree as an example, we introduce the construction of $BT_{\rho_x}^1$ subtrees (See Sec. IV-B2 and Sec. IV-B3 in our paper). For the $BT_{\rho_1}^1$, as the Condition node checks in Fig. 2, we adopt it to handle the case that the current state already satisfies the first justice goal and z , then we construction the Action node to hope the system could move to the next state that $z'_{|x} \wedge jx' = 2$, continuously to force the system to reach the second goal J_2^c .

Figure 2: The Structure of $BT_{\rho_1}^1$

For the $BT_{\rho_2}^1$, as illustrated in Fig. 3, it contains two *Sequence* subtrees and each is designed to handle the case that the current state is a $mY[1][r]$ state.

The $BT_{\rho_2}^1$ succeeds if one of its sequence subtrees returns *Success*. For a single *Sequence* subtree, such as the first in Fig. 3, it's expected to handle the case that the current state already satisfies $mY[1][2]$ but does not satisfy $mY[1][1]$, and then it would make the system move to the $mY[1][1]$ state and keep the jx equals to 1. Note that $z = \bigcup_{j \in \{1, \dots, n\}} mY[j][1]$, hence, once reached the $mY[j][1]$ states, means that the system already satisfies the j th justice goal, which then will be handled by $BT_{\rho_x}^1$.

Figure 3: Structure of BT_{ρ_2}

For the $BT_{\rho_3}^1$, as illustrated in Fig. 4, it has a similar structure with $BT_{\rho_2}^1$, because the level-2 (c.f., Sec. IV-B3) have been pruned as $i \in \{1\}$. We designed this subtree to handle the case that the current state satisfies $mX[\square][\square]$ states. Take the first subtree as an example, if the current is an $mX[1][1][1]$ state, and the environment is a mY'_y state, then we would like to make the system to move to the mY'_x state and remain the $jx' = 1$.

Figure 4: Structure of BT_{ρ_2}

Thus, by using the construction algorithm, we could synthesize a semantically correct and well-structured BT from the intermediate strategies from $GR(1)$ (i.e., the two arrays $mX[\square][\square]$ and $mY[\square]$, the system-winning set z).

4 Additional Experiments and Results

4.1 Experiment of RawBT with Pruning Strategies

We conducted additional experiments applying pruning strategies to RawBT, referred to as RawBT⁺. The experimental setup was identical to that of the other methods. Table 2 presents the experimental results for construction time, while Tables 3 and 4 show the static evaluation results for behavior trees, including tree size and balance. Finally, we ran the behavior trees, and the corresponding decision time results are presented in Table 5.

From the Table. 2 and Table. 3 we could see that, after incorporating the pruning algorithm, RawBT’s time to construct BTs has improved compared to before, with an average improvement of 12%. The size of the constructed behavior trees has also decreased by 12% on average. Notably, in the Cinderella scenario, the size of the pruned behavior tree matches that produced by EffBT. However, in other scenarios, the performance of RawBT with pruning still lags significantly behind EffBT.

Table 2: The Construction Time Results of GR(1), RawBT, RawBT⁺, EffBT#, and EffBT

Task		#Nodes ($\times 10k$)	Time _{RC} (sec)	Construction Time (sec)				
				GR(1)	RawBT	RawBT ⁺	EffBT	EffBT#
Frozen ⁺	8 \times 8	0.25	0.05	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
	16 \times 16	6.37	2.20	13.71	4.21	3.78	2.78	2.98
	24 \times 24	49.22	31.19	280.62	417.26	366.47	37.20	47.62
	32 \times 32	118.12	131.96	OOT	2355.65	2061.38	575.90	1015.64
Cinderella	N = 6, B = 12	0.59	0.35	1.46	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
	N = 7, B = 14	1.10	1.80	3.43	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
	N = 8, B = 16	2.54	19.03	35.84	0.11	0.10	0.08	0.08
	N = 9, B = 18	9.41	265.46	55.45	0.76	0.66	0.58	0.59
SYNTECH	ConvoyCar	0.58	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.004	0.002
	RobotArm	5.01	1.81	7.92	7.15	5.87	1.82	1.86
	Humanoid	0.42	0.04	0.03	0.06	0.05	0.02	0.02
	SelfParkingCar	0.71	0.48	0.71	0.10	0.08	0.01	0.01
	JobScheduler	1.98	0.69	56.06	888.65	637.89	3.02	3.41
	Tower of Hanoi	48.14	18.19	48.12	98.68	50.02	37.64	38.60

Furthermore, for the metric Balance, which evaluates the modularity and standardization of behavior tree modules, the results are presented in Table. 4. In summary, the pruning strategy enhances the Balance of behavior trees generated by the RawBT method. Specifically, pruning improves the structural balance of the behavior trees and, in most cases, improves their nodal balance, thereby enhancing the overall quality of the generated behavior trees.

Finally, we ran the behavior tree generated by RawBT five times and measured the average sum of the decision-making times over 5,000 steps, with the results presented in Table 5.

Table 3: Behavior Tree Size Results of RawBT, RawBT⁺, EffBT#, and EffBT

Task		BT Size			
		RawBT	RawBT ⁺	EffBT	EffBT#
Frozen ⁺	8 × 8	89	77	41	95
	16 × 16	839	704	408	939
	24 × 24	3464	2860	1698	3924
	32 × 32	7861	5581	3871	8966
Cinderella	N = 6, B = 12	23	6	6	18
	N = 7, B = 14	23	6	6	18
	N = 8, B = 16	23	6	6	18
	N = 9, B = 18	23	6	6	18
SYNTECH	ConvoyCar	47	33	20	46
	RobotArm	206	171	96	216
	Humanoid	161	133	110	150
	SelfParkingCar	352	272	201	333
	JobScheduler	1064	854	516	1186
	Tower of Hanoi	24599	18753	12296	28690

Table 4: Balance Results of BTs from RawBT, RawBT⁺, EffBT#, and EffBT

Task		Balance (Structural + Nodes')			
		RawBT	RawBT ⁺	EffBT	EffBT#
Frozen ⁺	8 × 8	0.80 (0.12+0.68)	0.90 (0.18+0.72)	1.77 (1.00+0.77)	1.45 (1.00+0.45)
	16 × 16	0.93 (0.07+0.86)	0.95 (0.12+0.83)	1.63 (0.82+0.81)	1.29 (0.81+0.48)
	24 × 24	0.96 (0.05+0.91)	0.97 (0.10+0.87)	1.62 (0.76+0.86)	1.24 (0.75+0.49)
	32 × 32	0.97 (0.04+0.93)	0.98 (0.10+0.88)	1.65 (0.76+0.89)	1.24 (0.75+0.49)
Cinderella	N = 6, B = 12	0.84 (0.50+0.34)	2.00 (1.00+1.00)	2.00 (1.00+1.00)	1.30 (1.00+0.30)
	N = 7, B = 14	0.84 (0.50+0.34)	2.00 (1.00+1.00)	2.00 (1.00+1.00)	1.30 (1.00+0.30)
	N = 8, B = 16	0.84 (0.50+0.34)	2.00 (1.00+1.00)	2.00 (1.00+1.00)	1.30 (1.00+0.30)
	N = 9, B = 18	0.84 (0.50+0.34)	2.00 (1.00+1.00)	2.00 (1.00+1.00)	1.30 (1.00+0.30)
SYNTECH	ConvoyCar	0.75 (0.23+0.52)	0.94 (0.33+0.61)	1.61 (1.00+0.61)	1.40 (1.00+0.40)
	RobotArm	0.87 (0.17+0.70)	0.88 (0.23+0.65)	1.11 (0.49+0.62)	0.91 (0.48+0.43)
	Humanoid	0.63 (0.08+0.55)	0.83 (0.15+0.68)	1.33 (0.79+0.54)	1.40 (0.84+0.56)
	SelfParkingCar	0.68 (0.06+0.62)	0.85 (0.17+0.68)	1.11 (0.58+0.53)	1.29 (0.68+0.61)
	JobScheduler	0.94 (0.08+0.86)	1.01 (0.18+0.83)	1.00 (0.20+0.80)	0.66 (0.19+0.47)
	Tower of Hanoi	1.00 (0.00+1.00)	1.00 (0.00+1.00)	2.00 (1.00+1.00)	1.51 (1.00+0.51)

Table 5: Execution Time of BTs from RawBT, RawBT⁺, EffBT#, and EffBT

Task		Execution (sec)			
		RawBT	RawBT ⁺	EffBT	EffBT#
Frozen ⁺	8 × 8	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.08
	16 × 16	0.26	0.21	0.19	0.30
	24 × 24	0.67	0.55	0.44	0.60
	32 × 32	1.28	0.96	0.78	0.91
Cinderella	N = 6, B = 12	5.62	4.21	3.98	4.59
	N = 7, B = 14	321.09	269.37	195.73	264.82
	N = 8, B = 16	36.22	28.53	23.81	30.23
	N = 9, B = 18	948.33	723.15	570.72	720.20
SYNTECH	ConvoyCar	0.27	0.25	0.22	0.34
	RobotArm	6.69	5.70	5.20	6.29
	Humanoid	0.88	0.61	0.57	0.72
	SelfParkingCar	0.89	0.77	0.70	0.93
	JobScheduler	13.42	10.92	8.96	10.52
	Tower of Hanoi	1.50	1.22	0.98	1.22

References

- [1] Arnaud Gotlieb. “Chapter Two - Constraint-Based Testing: An Emerging Trend in Software Testing”. In: ed. by Atif Memon. Vol. 99. Advances in Computers. Elsevier, 2015, pp. 67–101. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.adcom.2015.05.002>.